

FORMING CREATIVE THINKING SKILLS IN THE PROCESS OF TRAINING FUTURE VOCATIONAL EDUCATION TEACHERS

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ABSTRACT

In this article, in the process of training future teachers of vocational education, special attention is paid to the technology of formation of creative thinking skills and the improvement of creativity skills. Formation of creative abilities of teachers is considered one of the urgent problems today. For this reason, our article reveals the aspects that should be taken into account in order to improve the creative abilities of vocational education teachers.

In today's process of globalization, the development of modern technologies depends primarily on the intellectual potential of society, including the development of the education sector. Issues of the content and quality of education are considered a priority in society. In the developed and developing countries of the world, special attention is paid to the technology of education. Ways to develop education and increase its effectiveness are being sought, and the introduction of pedagogical technologies has become the focus of reforms in the field of education.

President of the Republic of Uzbekistan Sh. M. Mirziyoyev: "There are complex tasks ahead of us in terms of educating young people, training and retraining personnel in psychology and various other fields. It is important to solve another problem: it is the professional level of pedagogues and teaching staff, their special knowledge. In this regard, it is necessary to create an environment that actively supports the processes of education, spiritual and educational maturity, and the formation of real values.

Fundamental improvement of the education system in our country is recognized as a priority direction of state policy. In order to achieve this goal, new models of education are being created, the theoretical and methodological foundations of which are scientifically and practically proven by leading experts and scientists.

In the Concept of the development of the higher education system in the Republic of Uzbekistan until 2030, it is necessary to increase the quality of training of highly educated specialists, students' independent education, critical and creative thinking, systematic analysis, formation of entrepreneurial skills, strengthening of competencies in the educational process. introduction of targeted methods and technologies, orientation of the educational process to the formation of practical skills, in this regard, advanced pedagogical technologies,

educational programs and teaching-methodical materials based on international educational standards are widely used in the educational process measures for implementation were determined.[1]

Creativity describes a person as a whole or his specific features, mental sharpness. Also, creativity is reflected as an important factor of talent. A teacher does not become a creator by himself. His creative ability is formed through consistent study and work on himself over a period of time.

In recent years, in the educational system of leading foreign countries, special and serious attention has been paid to the issue of the formation of creativity qualities in teachers and students. Bronson, Merryman (2010), Ken Robinson (2007), Fisher, Frey (2008), Begetto, Kaufman (2013), Ali (2011), Treffinger (2008), and b. many studies conducted by, can be seen from their results. A 2007 book by the one and only Ken Robinson, Is School Stifling Creativity? The video has been viewed 5 million times on YouTube. In addition, teachers are seriously engaged in learning the basics of creativity (Begetto, Kaufman, 2013). Literature is being published on the formation and development of teachers' creative approach to pedagogical activity. Non-traditional lessons based on videos prepared by the Department of Education are being organized (Ali, 2011; Department of Education, 2013). Despite significant practical work, most teachers still do not master the experience of how to effectively form creative qualities in themselves and students.

Not so long ago, the concept of "creativity" began to be used in modern pedagogy. However, the need for innovative and creative approaches to the teaching process is increasing.

The professional growth and development of a person as a specialist is manifested as a process according to its essence. Professional maturity is an important period of human ontogeny, starting with professional development and development ideas (14-17 years old) and ending professional activity (55-60 years old). The formation and development of a creative person depends on the mutual compatibility of changes in his inner and outer world, socio-economic conditions and human ontogenesis - from birth to the end of his life, the content of activity that requires continuity and succession. It is known that professional experience is reflected as an integration of knowledge, skills and abilities. However, mastering the skills of professional and creative activity is not only the integration of practical skills and qualifications, the development of methods and tools for the effective organization of activities as a specialist, but also awareness of the methodology of professional creativity, the development of creative thinking and creative it requires adequate mastering of personal qualities of character. The formation of a creative person can be defined as the development of a person in terms of creative activities performed in a mutually compatible way and creation of creative products. The pace and scope of this process depends on biological and social factors, the activity and creative qualities of a person, as well as existing conditions, important vital and professional events.

Educational system management bodies focus on achieving high efficiency in educational institutions every year. For this purpose, the curriculum is developed, new textbooks are created. This helps both students and teachers to grow professionally. Conducted practical actions create the need to achieve achievements and progress in students

to a certain extent, help to develop their learning abilities to some extent. However, at the end of the academic year, there are no high-level positive results in students' mastery of subjects in higher education institutions. Many students have lost interest in education. As a result, teachers are not thinking about organizing professional activities with pleasure as before. Although the governing bodies of the education system have decided to take new measures to change the activities of teachers who do not want to teach students who do not want to learn, the situation is still remains unchanged. What is the reason for this? Maybe the pre-planned lessons are not interesting for students, maybe the fact that the content of education is set in a certain pattern does not give students any incentive. Avoid pre-planning of educational activities, form and develop critical, creative thinking in students, force them to think creatively, come up with new ideas, change the attitude to education, encourage them to achieve achievements will be the main factor in promotion. The missing factor in training sessions is creativity. In order to fully understand the general nature of the process of developing creative qualities in a person, it is necessary to first understand the meaning of the concept of "creativity". According to Ken Robinson, "creativity is a set of original ideas with their own value" (Azzam, 2009). And Gardner explains the concept in his research as follows: "creativity is a practical action performed by a person, which should reflect a certain novelty and have a certain practical value." In terms of Emebail's (1989) approach, creativity means "the possession of highly unusual skills along with thorough knowledge of a specific domain."

Many studies have different views on the relationship between intelligence and creativity. One group of researchers claims that there is no connection between them, while the representatives of the second group claim that the level of creativity and intelligence are related to each other (Kim, 2005). The concept of "creativity" reflects cultural diversity. For Westerners, creativity is generally considered a novelty. They emphasize that creativity is based on unconventionality, curiosity, imagination, sense of humor, and freedom (Murdoch, Ganim, 1993; Sternberg, 1985). Easterners, on the contrary, understand creativity as a process of rebirth of goodness (Hui, Sternberg, 2002; Rudovich, Hui, 1997; Rudovich, Yue, 2000). Although Westerners and Easterners have different views on creativity, representatives of both cultures value this quality and possessing it highly (Kaufman, Lan, 2012). Many teachers have creativity in themselves. they believe that the ability does not exist. This can be justified by two different reasons: firstly, most teachers cannot explain what the concept of "creativity" really means; secondly, they are unaware of what qualities are directly reflected in the basis of creativity. At this point, it is worth noting that every person has the ability to be creative by nature. So, how can teachers demonstrate their creativity? Here's Patti Drapeau's advice: "If you don't think you're creative, I suggest you start organizing creative thinking classes now. In fact, it's not about whether or not you are creative and creative, but about organizing classes in the spirit of creativity and trying new ideas in practice." According to Patti Drapeau, creative thinking is, first of all, comprehensive thinking about a specific issue. Multidisciplinary thinking requires students to rely on multiple ideas when completing assignments, problems, and tasks. In contrast, one-sided thinking is based on only one correct idea. In observation, it is impossible to deny one of the one-sided and multi-sided thinking on the issue.

Therefore, one and all-round thinking is equally important in the formation of creativity. That is, when completing a task, solving a problem, the student looks for several options for a solution (multidirectional thinking), and then stops at the only correct solution that guarantees the most optimal result (unidirectional thinking). Based on the above-mentioned ideas, the concept of "creativity" can be interpreted as follows:

Creativity (lat., ing. "create" - creation, "creative" - creator) is the creative ability of an individual that describes the readiness to produce new ideas and is part of talent as an independent factor.

A person's creativity is manifested in his thinking, communication, feelings, and certain types of activities. Creativity describes a person as a whole or his specific characteristics. Creativity is also reflected as an important factor of talent. In addition, creativity determines mental sharpness, "ensures the active involvement of students in the educational process."

Creativity is the ability to create something new, unique, a mental process that leads to new thinking, original ideas and solutions. From the definition given to the concept, it is clear that creativity, like the qualities of initiative and creative approach to work, does not necessarily have to be innate or a divine gift. As long as creativity is a mental process, there are certainly endless ways and methods to improve and develop the human mind, to use its unlimited possibilities.

In this regard, we can interpret creativity in the views of the thinker Abu Ali Ibn Sina. In his opinion, a teacher cannot guide his student to creative thinking without identifying his inclination, desire, activity, ability, talent and ability.

Thinker Jalalidin Davani in his work entitled "Ethics of Jalali" emphasized that in order to cultivate intellectual ability and intellectual talent in human qualities, it is necessary to be clever, intelligent, understanding, creative, and to remember knowledge quickly and to understand.

We can also see creativity in the views of the thinker Zahiriddin Muhammad Babur: He understands the problematic situation and creativity as one of the main ways of development of the human personality, and he used it effectively in his work.[2]

This is what Albert Einstein meant when he said, "Imagination is more important than knowledge." The word "creativity" was first used in 1922 by the American scientist D. Simpson. With this term, a person described the ability to abandon the stereotyped, habitual way of thinking.

In foreign countries, teachers, like specialists in all fields, determine whether they have creative qualities and their level. For this, they pass a test based on E.P. Torrens in 1987, which determines whether a person has creative thinking. This test provides an opportunity to evaluate the creativity of a person and its level according to such criteria as activity in organizing creative activities, quick thinking, originality and refinement. The answers to the questions suggested by the reader should reflect these four criteria. According to E.P. Torrens, the following is explained on the basis of the concept of "creativity":

- to put forward a problem or scientific hypothesis;
- checking and changing the hypothesis;
- identifying the problem based on the formation of decision results;

- sensitivity to the conflict between knowledge and practical actions in finding a solution to a problem.

Creative thinking can be clearly reflected in every social sphere. The teacher's creativity is reflected in his creative approach to the organization of professional activities organized by him[3].

Due to the teacher's lack of creativity, even though the students have interesting and wonderful ideas, they are slow to express them. For this reason, the methods used in the educational process are determined by the fact that they do not serve to form students' free and independent thinking skills. The tools and strategies recommended by the author are useful for teachers in developing students' creativity and develop students' interest and desire to learn academic subjects.

The creativity of the pedagogue in professional activity is manifested in various forms. They are:

<i>Basic forms</i>	
Regulatory documents (in academic subjects DTS, curriculum and preparation of plans)	Creation of educational resources (textbook, educational and methodological manual, recommendations, dictionary, encyclopedia, atlas, workbook, etc.)
Preparation of projects of educational process and spiritual educational work	Educational information, control and test assignments formation
The educational process is interesting, lively, lively organization	Scientific research lead successfully
Active participation in scientific and methodical conferences, giving speeches	Publication of scientific, scientific-methodical and methodical works
<i>Submission of periodic reports, certification</i>	

It helps to clarify the ideas of teachers and future pedagogues about organizing the process of creative thinking. "M: in the process of studying the essence of the concept of information on the basis of the strategy of brainstorming, future teachers should first of all have an understanding of what the strategy is and how to use it." It is worth noting that the concepts of "stratification" and "periodization" become important in the process of development. So, what do these two concepts mean?

Differentiation (lat. "diferentia" - "difference", "grading") - division of the whole into different stages or levels.

Periodization (Greek. "peridos" - "turning around in a circle") - the division of a certain event into time units covering a certain completed process. In creative development, the period and stage in the life of each person are important. So: The period of development of creativity is a certain period of time when the development of certain creative qualities is completed. The stage of development of creativity - the level of development of certain creative qualities, accordingly, in certain periods and stages, creative qualities and skills of creative activity are developed in pedagogues.

Future pedagogues with creative thinking:

- expresses ideas that have not occurred to other future pedagogues;
- chooses a unique way of expressing themselves;
- sometimes asks unrelated or unusual questions;
- enjoys open-ended tasks;
- prefers to discuss ideas based on clear evidence;

He chooses an unconventional approach to finding a solution to a problem.

- Personal creativity qualities are listed as follows:

- Creative direction;
- Ability to think logically;
- Erudition (knowledge);
- Rich imagination;
- Creative effectiveness and initiative;
- Full demonstration of one's creativity;
- Ability to reflect;
- Emotional richness;
- Ability to take risks;
- Ownership of thinking speed; - Development of inner intuition;
- The ability to put forward unique (original) ideas;
- Possession of innovative ability;
- Possession of high artistic values;
- Ability to make new decisions based on existing experience and knowledge. In addition

to the qualities of creativity, pedagogues should also have the following qualifications, which represent the ability to organize creative activities:

It allows teachers to organize creative activities

skill groups:

- 1) cognitive (gnostic) qualifications;
- 2) design skills;
- 3) creative-practical (constructive) skills; research skills;
- 4) accessibility to communication (communicative) skills;
- 5) organizational skills;
- 6) consistency (procedural) skills;
- 7) technical-technological qualifications, the essence of these groups of qualifications is

explained below:

Knowledge (Gnostic) Qualifications:

- Determination of educational and educational tasks, taking into account the age and individual characteristics of future pedagogues, socio-psychological uniqueness of the team;
- didactic, psychological and methodical planning and analysis of the educational process based on modern educational requirements;
- being able to reasonably choose effective forms, methods and tools for organizing education and training processes;

- to be able to determine the results of the mastering of materials by the future pedagogues based on the requirements of the curriculum, the level of education and development of students;

- to carry out various types of work on the development of interest, needs and activities of future pedagogues;

- carrying out various educational activities in class, extracurricular conditions, extended day groups, circles, clubs or societies;

- carrying out individual work with future pedagogues and their parents;

- formation of future pedagogues' need for a healthy lifestyle, personal and general hygiene skills, first aid skills;

- it is necessary to use various instructional weapons, modern technical tools, information and advanced pedagogical technologies in the educational process.

Design Skills:

- creating projects of lessons or educational events;

- creating a technological map of a lesson or educational event;

- step-by-step explanation of the essence of the lesson or educational event;

- clearly defining the purpose of educational or educational activity;

- determination of tasks appropriate to the purpose;

- to describe the didactic, educational and developmental goals of the educational material;

- formation of educational or educational material content;

- ensuring mutual consistency between several pieces of information that reveal the content of educational or educational material;

- developing a system of questions that encourage future pedagogues to think independently;

- justification of the methodical structure of the lesson or educational event;

- to determine the system of pedagogical tasks performed during a lesson or educational event;

- use of various modern approaches to the presentation of new material;

- development of test tasks with certain consistency;

- justification of the process of diagnosing the level of knowledge of future pedagogues;

- to create a mechanism for evaluating the level of education and development of the team of future pedagogues and individual students.

The obtained conclusions and recommendations serve to ensure the quality of the educational process, increase the effectiveness of spiritual and educational work, and improve the process of teaching based on a creative approach to the activities of educational institutions.

The effective organization of professional activity by the teacher in these forms depends on the level of his creativity.

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